

Traumatic Extraperitoneal Rectal Injury with Anal Sphincter Disruption: A Case Report

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Abstract

Traumatic rectal injuries are rare but potentially life-threatening, particularly in blunt trauma, where diagnosis may be delayed and morbidity remains high. Management strategies have evolved from dogmatic approaches toward selective, anatomy-based treatment. We report the case of a 21-year-old man who presented following a fall onto sharp metallic bars from a height of 1.5 meters, resulting in direct posterior perineal trauma. Clinical examination revealed generalized abdominal guarding and a low posterior anal laceration associated with sphincter atony. Plain abdominal radiography demonstrated pneumoperitoneum. Surgical exploration identified multiple extraperitoneal rectal injuries, complete anal sphincter disruption, and sigmoid parietal pneumatosis without transmural colonic perforation. Management consisted of transanal repair of rectal wounds, sphincter reconstruction, and protective sigmoid colostomy. Postoperative recovery was uneventful, with restoration of bowel continuity two months later and satisfactory sphincter function. This case highlights the diagnostic challenges and therapeutic considerations of blunt rectal trauma. Early recognition, systematic evaluation combining imaging and endoscopic assessment, and tailored surgical management are essential to optimize outcomes. Selective primary repair with judicious fecal diversion remains a safe and effective strategy in appropriately selected patients

Keywords: Rectal trauma, Extraperitoneal rectal injury, Anal sphincter disruption, Pneumoperitoneum, Fecal diversion, Transanal repair.

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Introduction

Rectal trauma is an uncommon but potentially life-threatening injury, accounting for approximately 1–3% of civilian trauma cases and up to

5% in military settings [1,2]. Despite its low incidence, rectal injury is associated with significant morbidity due to delayed diagnosis, high rates of associated pelvic and abdominal injuries, and the risk of pelvic

sepsis [3]. The rectum's deep pelvic location provides relative protection; however, this same anatomic characteristic contributes to diagnostic challenges, particularly in blunt trauma where clinical signs may be subtle or absent [4].

Rectal injuries are broadly classified according to mechanism (penetrating vs. blunt) and anatomic location relative to the peritoneal reflection (intra-abdominal vs. extra-abdominal) [5]. These distinctions are critical, as they directly influence management strategies. Historically, treatment principles were largely derived from military experience and centered on the "four Ds": debridement, diversion, presacral drainage, and distal rectal washout [6]. In recent decades, however, civilian data have challenged the routine application of these dogmatic approaches, leading to more selective and evidence-based management algorithms [7,8].

Advances in computed tomography (CT), endoscopic techniques, damage-control surgery, and critical care have significantly improved outcomes. Contemporary practice emphasizes accurate diagnosis, tailored surgical intervention, and avoidance of unnecessary fecal diversion when safe [9].

We report a rare case of extra-abdominal rectal injury with anal sphincter disruption following a fall onto a sharp metallic object. This case illustrates the diagnostic challenges and highlights the importance of individualized surgical management based on injury pattern and severity, in line with modern trauma care principles.

Case Presentation

A 21-year-old patient with no significant past medical history presented to the emergency department after a fall onto a sharp metallic object ("iron bars") from a height of approximately 1.5 meters, with direct impact to the posterior perineum. He complained of diffuse abdominal pain associated with rectal bleeding.

Figure 1: Image of the traumatic object ("iron bars") responsible for the injury

Clinical examination revealed generalized abdominal guarding. Digital rectal examination identified a breach of continuity at the 6 o'clock position, extending over 3 cm from the anal verge, associated with sphincter atony. In view of the abdominal guarding, a plain abdominal radiograph was performed, demonstrating pneumoperitoneum (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Plain abdominal radiograph showing bilateral pneumoperitoneum

Figure 3: Image of the anal lesion

Figure 4: Intraoperative image showing sigmoid parietal pneumatosis

The patient was subsequently taken to the operating room. Following induction of general anesthesia, he was placed in the lithotomy position, and a proctologic examination was performed, exploring up to 20 cm of the rectocolic mucosa. In addition to the initially described lesion, re-evaluation under anesthesia revealed complete disruption of the anal sphincters, as well as two additional rectal lesions: one located at the 3 o'clock position, 9 cm from the anal verge, measuring 2 cm, and another at the 7 o'clock position, 5 cm from the anal verge, measuring 1.5 cm. Both lesions were non–full-thickness.

Exploratory laparotomy was performed through a midline incision. Surgical exploration revealed sigmoid colon parietal pneumatosis without any identifiable transmural colonic injury. There were no signs of peritonitis, including absence of peritoneal effusion or fibrinous exudates.

Surgical management consisted of transanal repair of the two rectal wounds, sphincter reconstruction using U-shaped sutures with repair of the anal wound, and a protective sigmoid colostomy. Postoperative recovery was uneventful. At one-month follow-up, the patient demonstrated good sphincter tone, and restoration of bowel continuity was successfully performed two months after the trauma.

Discussion

Penetrating trauma remains the most common cause of rectal injury in civilian populations, accounting for approximately 70–85% of cases, predominantly from gunshot wounds and stab injuries [1,10]. Blunt rectal trauma is less frequent (5–10%) but is often associated with high-energy mechanisms such as motor vehicle collisions, crush injuries, falls from height, and pelvic fractures [4,11]. Blunt injuries are more likely to involve the extraperitoneal rectum and are associated with higher rates of missed diagnosis and delayed complications [12].

Early diagnosis of rectal trauma is essential to reduce morbidity and mortality. Initial assessment follows Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS) principles, with rectal evaluation forming part of the secondary survey [13]. Digital rectal examination alone has limited sensitivity and should not be relied upon to exclude injury [14].

Contrast-enhanced CT scan of the abdomen and pelvis is the cornerstone of diagnosis in hemodynamically stable patients, particularly in blunt trauma [5,9]. Findings suggestive of rectal injury include extraluminal air, perirectal fluid, bowel wall thickening, mesorectal fat stranding, and associated pelvic fractures [8]. Rigid proctoscopy or flexible sigmoidoscopy remains the gold standard for direct visualization of rectal mucosal injuries and should be performed when rectal trauma is suspected [7,15].

Management of rectal trauma is dictated by injury location, severity, mechanism, and associated injuries.

Intraperitoneal rectal injuries are treated similarly to colonic injuries. Primary repair is preferred for small, non-destructive injuries, while segmental resection with or without anastomosis may be required for extensive damage or devascularization [9,16]. Routine fecal diversion is not recommended in stable patients without significant contamination [10].

Extraperitoneal rectal injuries present a greater therapeutic challenge due to limited surgical access. Current evidence supports a selective approach. Primary transanal repair is favored when technically feasible, particularly for low-grade injuries [7,17]. Proximal fecal diversion is reserved for destructive injuries, severe contamination, associated pelvic fractures, or hemodynamic instability [6,8]. Routine presacral drainage and distal rectal washout are no longer universally recommended, as multiple studies have failed to demonstrate clear benefit and have reported increased morbidity [7,10].

Minimally invasive techniques, including transanal endoscopic repair and endoscopic clipping, have emerged as safe and effective options in

selected extraperitoneal injuries, further reducing the need for diversion [18].

Complications following rectal trauma include pelvic sepsis, abscess formation, fistulae, strictures, and long-term functional impairment such as fecal incontinence [3,12]. Blunt trauma and delayed diagnosis are consistently associated with worse outcomes [11]. When diversion is required, colostomy reversal should be performed after confirmation of rectal healing, typically using contrast studies and endoscopic assessment [16].

Overall mortality ranges from 3% to 10% in civilian series, largely driven by associated injuries rather than the rectal lesion itself [1,9]. Adherence to modern, evidence-based algorithms has significantly reduced morbidity compared with historical outcomes.

Conclusion

Traumatic rectal injury remains a complex clinical entity requiring a high index of suspicion and a structured diagnostic approach. Advances in imaging, endoscopy, and trauma surgery have shifted management away from rigid dogma toward selective, anatomy-based strategies. Intraperitoneal injuries are managed similarly to colonic trauma, while extraperitoneal injuries benefit from individualized treatment, with selective primary repair and judicious use of fecal diversion. Routine application of presacral drainage and distal washout is no longer supported in civilian practice. Early diagnosis, appropriate surgical decision-making, and multidisciplinary trauma care are essential to optimize outcomes and minimize long-term morbidity.

References

- [1] Clemens MS, Peace KM, Yi F. Rectal trauma: evidence-based practices. *Clin Colon Rectal Surg.* 2018;31(1):17–23. doi:10.1055/s-0037-1609024.
- [2] Petrone P, Rodríguez Velandia W, Dziaková J, Marini CP. Treatment of complex perineal trauma: a review of the literature. *Cir Esp.* 2016;94(6):313–322. doi:10.1016/j.ciresp.2015.12.006.
- [3] Jeganathan AN, Cannon JW, Bleier JIS. Anal and perineal injuries. *Clin Colon Rectal Surg.* 2018;31(1):24–29. doi:10.1055/s-0037-1609025.
- [4] Fortuna L, Bottari A, Somigli R, Giannesi S. Management of a traumatic anorectal full-thickness laceration. *J Trauma Inj.* 2022;35(4):215–218. doi:10.20408/jti.2022.0049.
- [5] Emigh B, Inaba K, Schellenberg M. Contemporary diagnosis and management of traumatic rectal injuries. *Surg Pract Sci.* 2021;4:100024. doi:10.1016/j.sipas.2021.100024.
- [6] Lavenson GS, Cohen A. Management of rectal injuries. *Am J Surg.* 1971;122(2):226–230. doi:10.1016/0002-9610(71)90318-9.
- [7] Schellenberg M, Koller S, de Moya M, et al. Diagnosis and management of traumatic rectal injury: a Western Trauma Association algorithm. *J Trauma Acute Care Surg.* 2023;95(4):731–739. doi:10.1097/TA.0000000000003927.
- [8] Demetriades D, Velmahos GC, Cornwell EE 3rd, et al. Selective management of rectal injuries. *Ann Surg.* 2001;233(4):587–592. doi:10.1097/00000658-200104000-00017.
- [9] Brown CVR, Teixeira PGR, Furay E, et al. Contemporary management of rectal injuries: a multicenter study. *J Trauma Acute Care Surg.* 2018;84(2):225–233. doi:10.1097/TA.0000000000001733.
- [10] Hahn KY, Ko SY, Lee WS, Kim YH. Extraperitoneal rectal laceration secondary to blunt trauma: successful transanal endoscopic repair. *Chin Med J (Engl).* 2017;130(19):2384–2386. doi:10.4103/0366-6999.215339.
- [11] Naranjo Cardenas D, et al. Blunt anorectal trauma: case report and literature review. *Rev Argent Coloproct.* 2024;35(1):1–6.

- [12] Ivatury RR, et al. Diagnosis and management of rectal injuries. *Surg Clin North Am.* 1996;76(4):685–700. doi:10.1016/S0039-6109(05)70479-6.
- [13] American College of Surgeons. ATLS®: Advanced Trauma Life Support. 10th ed. Chicago (IL): American College of Surgeons; 2018.
- [14] Esposito TJ, et al. The role of digital rectal examination in trauma. *J Trauma.* 1995;39(2):394–398. doi:10.1097/00005373-199508000-00032.
- [15] Steele SR, et al. Practice management guidelines for colorectal injuries. *Dis Colon Rectum.* 2011;54(12):1464–1475. doi:10.1097/DCR.0b013e31823122b1.
- [16] Miller PR, et al. Colostomy closure following rectal trauma. *Am Surg.* 2002;68(1):89–94.
- [17] Emigh B, Inaba K. Transanal approaches to extraperitoneal rectal trauma. *Trauma Surg Acute Care Open.* 2020;5(1):e000488. doi:10.1136/tsaco-2020-000488.
- [18] Hahn KY, Ko SY, Lee WS, Kim YH. Endoscopic management of blunt rectal injuries. *Chin Med J (Engl).* 2017;130(19):2384–2386. doi:10.4103/0366-6999.215339.